

WOMEN IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: SCIENCE AND QUALITY EDUCATION

3RD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

Barqaror rivojlanishda ayollar: fan va sifatli ta'lim

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Kalit soʻzlar: Ayollar,
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Annotatsiya: Dunyo aholisining yarmi ayollarni ifodalaydi. Ayollar butun dunyo bo'ylab STEM (fan, texnologiya, muhandislik va matematika) sohasida faol. 11 fevral kuni Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti ushbu sohalarda ayollarning faolligini oshirish va yangi 2030 kun tartibi maqsadlarini qo'llab-quvvatlash maqsadida Xalqaro fan va ta'lim sohasida ayollar kunini nishonladi. Bosh assambleya va Xavfsizlik kengashining 2016-yilda qabul qilingan tinchlikni saqlash bo'yicha rezolyutsiyalari BMTga a'zo davlatlarning inson huquqlari bo'yicha xalqaro qonunlar va standartlarga asoslangan ustuvor yo'nalishlari o'zgarganini ko'rsatdi. Rezolyutsiyada tinchlikni saqlash 2030 yilga mo'ljallangan kun tartibining fan va ta'lim sohasida ayollarni barqaror rivojlantirish bo'yicha xalqqa yo'naltirilgan yondashuviga asoslanishini ta'minlash majburiyatini olgan. Shu bois ayollarning ta'lim olishi va ilm-fanga qo'shgan hissasi barqaror rivojlanish uchun tramplin vazifasini o'taydi. Muvozanat va umumiy maqsadlarga erishish uchun raqobatbardosh hamkorlik qilish uchun raqobatni shafqatsiz o'zgartirish uchun etakchi sifatida ayollar salohiyati. Shu nuqtai nazardan, ayollarning bugungi va kelajak uchun zarur bo'lgan iste'dodlarini e'tirof etishning ayni vaqti. Ushbu maqola uzoq muddatli o'sish va porloq kelajak uchun ayollar ta'limi va ilm-faniga oid turli mavzularda tushuncha berishga qaratilgan.

Women in Sustainable Development: Science and Quality Education

Key words: Women, Development, Sustainability, Education, Science

Abstract: Half of the world's population represents women. Women are active worldwide in STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) fields. On February 11, the United Nations observed International Day of Women in Science and Education to encourage increased women involvement in these fields and to support the goals of the new 2030 Agenda. The general assembly and security council's resolutions on sustaining peace and adopted in 2016 have demonstrated a shift in the mind set priorities of the UN member states grounded international human right laws and standards. The resolution committed to ensure that sustaining peace is based on the people centered approach of 2030 agenda for sustainable development of women in science and education. Therefore, women's education and contribution to science act as a springboard to sustainable development. Women potential as a leader to make changes competition ruthless into cooperating competitively for balancing and attaining common goals. In this aspect the high time is to recognize the talents of women which are essential for today and for future as well. This article aims to provide insight on various themes relating to women's education and science for long-term growth and a bright future.

Женщины в устойчивом развитии: наука и качественное образование

Ключевые слова: женщины, развитие, устойчивость, образование, наука

Аннотация: Женщины составляют половину населения мира. Женщины активно работают в областях STEM (наука, технология, инженерия и математика) по всему миру. 11 февраля Организация Объединенных Наций отметила Международный день женщин в науке и образовании, чтобы продвигать деятельность женщин в этих областях и поддерживать цели новой Повестки дня на период до 2030 года. Принятые в 2016 году резолюции Генеральной Ассамблеи и Совета Безопасности о миротворчестве свидетельствовали об изменении приоритетов государств-членов ООН на основе международных законов и стандартов в области прав человека. Резолюция обязуется обеспечить, чтобы Повестка дня для мира на период до 2030 года основывалась на ориентированном на человека подходе к устойчивому развитию женщин в науке и образовании. Таким образом, образование женщин и их вклад в науку служат трамплином для устойчивого развития. Потенциал женщин как лидеров безжалостно трансформировать конкуренцию в конкурентное сотрудничество для достижения баланса и достижения общих целей. В этом контексте настало время признать таланты женщин сегодня и в будущем. Эта статья призвана дать представление о различных темах, связанных с женским образованием и наукой, для долгосрочного роста и светлого будущего.

Introduction

United Nation General Assembly held its 57th meeting in December 2002, from 2005 to 2014 UNGA proclaimed the UN decade for Education for Sustainable Development. It highlights universal education i.e., education for all as an important and necessary component for attaining sustainable development. The vision and mission for this development are to make a world where everyone gets an opportunity to benefit from quality education, positive transformation, learned behavior and values, and a required lifestyle for future sustainability. The 2030 agenda adopted by United Nations General Assembly for sustainable development is to maintain the framework and to be agreed on the development internationally. This gives success to the Millennium Development Goals it shows environmental and economic sustainability for inclusive and peaceful societies.

Women are the backbone of our society. whether be a part of the family, community, workplace, or as a homemaker, employer, job seeker, or contributor to social well-being. From the perspective of economic development, women scientist plays an essential role in changing ‘intolerable worldwide’ into developmental opportunities. Women know for further development knowledge has been applied for entrepreneurial actions. To acquire the level of wisdom that alone can bridge the tremendous gap between starting points and ambitious objectives, knowledge in women has been blended with cultural values, whether they be global, local, or national. This new approach is not only engaging the women but also identifying their potential and talent, harmonizing socially as well as creative power.

Quality education empowers women to increase as well as enhance their well-being, and social and economic gains. Women scientists are underrepresented in senior university management and professional positions, they are excluded from the creation of development policies, they are also discriminated against when applying for leadership positions in research, as well as lack the status and the capacity to produce excellence in both research and education, they are also not given the recognition they deserve in the form of awards or other kinds. The views

on women's social role are old, direct and indirect discrimination based on exploitation, and a lack of good child education was cited as significant factors. According to Lawson if there would be a low number of women's representation in positions of decision making this has affected the passing of laws and bills which could make a change in the lives of many people. It is also believed that quality education for women helps attain strategies of five goals in sustainable development. Therefore, women's quality education and contribution to science act as a springboard to sustainable development.

Contributions of women in science and Education

To maintain the environment, it is far too common to think about sustainable development as just the need to reduce consumption. People majority around the world are not enthusiastic to fulfill the requirements. The poor people oppose the requirements and demands with their statement that for a long time, they reached their consumption limit and are entitled to a larger share in the future. whereas rich people do not like limitations. Strategies in sustainable development are needed which provide a brighter future for everyone. Women should not be giving importance to materialistic things but represent a new set of values that place greater emphasis on wealth and togetherness as well as a greater sense of humanity's obligation to the natural world. The word 'sustainable' means lower consumption and better quality of life which would raise the higher standard of living. Therefore, the sustainable development of women should be easily understood through their progress in quality increased in every activity, especially in science and quality education. This quality helps women for better knowledge and achievements in technology, natural science, humanities as well as a social science. This means that women have an efficient contribution to the treasure of science as well as in local and national expertise they also show their integration of knowledge worldwide. The value system has been improved when its talks about women's qualities therefore, wisdom can only be created when knowledge is connected with ethics. Whereas in terms of new knowledge science continue to be

the main source, and the value system is first based on culture. Women are the one who strengthens as well as introduced culture and values to develop or care for harmony, health, beauty, and the environment. Tradition and change are the two connections that show the unique role of women in science. This supports values in women coping, accepting changes, and mastering humanity in nature.

Women scientists in health and promotes well being

The issues of the population are complex to explain in detail here – they get, and deserve, attention at various specific meetings however the two issues are significant and highlighted

Rapid growth of population in many countries because of poverty resulting in unemployment as well as decreasing the living standard.

Most countries face economic problems because of an increase in the population if strategies are not adopted. This brings out the social tension between the active and retired population

Women's equality is a necessary condition for solving any of the demographic issues. Women in science take more initiative and participation in research for maintaining a balanced growth in the population and this shows the result of quality education of women for reproductive health. Women also improve and emphasize socio-cultural values like care for home and life, protection and respect for children and old people as well as family spirit. The globally developed part should learn and understand these from developing countries where social involvement, as well as wider family, are still respected highly.

Women scientists focused their initiative on R&D-based learning

Women in science are especially accountable for implementing education reforms based on all four pillars identified by the committee on education for the 21st century since new approaches need to become a mainstream component of education for the 21st century:

Learning what to do: to concentrate and strengthen the power of one's ability to learn, to develop and nurture a sharp mind, mindful training to memory for information should be selected appropriately.

Learning doing it: connecting quality education and knowledge with skills, creating innovative techniques, abilities, and approaches, planning in work, enhancing the components of knowledge in every activity, and developing competition and intelligence in the group to achieve goals.

Learning becoming it: developing and creating abilities (physical, intellectual) creativity, imagination as well as scientific reasoning, emotions, language skills, and responsibility.

Learning living it together: living together with family, producers, citizens, inventors as well as members of the community.

Technology and science are the two main factors that dynamically increase and the result shows lead time shorter than years. Women learn to develop innovatively and inquiry approaches. R&D-based learning is important for women in higher education. Many colleges and universities place a high focus on research while giving education only passing consideration. Nevertheless, in the coming decades, education will be the deciding factor in development. This time is now for women in science to grab leadership in this education sector.

Women scientists for eradication of poverty, working together, and peace

Degradation in the environment as well as poverty are serious and major problems worldwide. Whereas women worldwide are harmonious in society which shows serious efforts when it demands a developed country. The expenditure of Gross Domestic Product per capita ranges from \$300 to \$30000 every year. Whereas high GDP countries are also there but few. The large majority of the population worldwide is living in poverty whereas, less of investment or 2% goes toward defense which means international help is worse even. Overcoming poverty should be addressed by women in science. Women initiated the two tasks: firstly, it significantly demands stronger assistance and consistency for development in

underdeveloped regions. The globalization process has made Europe overburdened by a western cultural perspective. As we all know that countries cannot live in peace if people are starving because the world is one. Secondly, the pervasive concept as well as false clarifications that a simple transfer of wealth may lead to world prosperity. Today global GDP is divided by the population worldwide the result would be all come under poverty. Women in science handle more strongly by developing and creating wealth, higher quality products, managing social and economic conditions more efficiently as well as maintaining a new environment-friendly process. Women in science show their talent in reaching other values which are required today and even more can be required tomorrow also. Development of group intelligence, spirit, leadership approaches, and knowledge transferrable in decision-making and production processes in any type of work, enhancing the knowledge objective with the cultural values are required in these values. Women introduced all of these into academic life as well encouraged to take leads toward sustainable development. So, there will be no problem for women in science to prove their scientific quality as well as equality.

Conclusion

Women in science and quality education has much stronger contribution, engagement as well as discovering new knowledge. Women not only showing the contribution but also developing economic potential and harmonizing social power which is vital for sustainable development. Women's Participation and contribution have been highly significant to the nation's sustainability. Therefore, women need to empower economically as well as educationally. So, in order to widening the research organization and universities women playing an important role by developing them into research centers, innovation and education. In order to get the women equality as a whole. This engagement is required in much more efficient way. Women in science and women in general both have the ability and potential for making a major contribution to sustainable development through their understanding particularly in the role of technology, benefits, omitting and judging

the unwanted effects of science and education on environment and society. Women potential as a leader to make changes competition ruthless into cooperating competitively for balancing and attaining common goals. In this aspect the high time is to recognize the talents of women which are essential for today and for future as well.